

Hybrid Lightwave/RF Cooperative Networks with Non-Orthogonal Multiple Access

Yue Xiao, Panagiotis D. Diamantoulakis, *Senior Member, IEEE*, Zequn Fang, Zheng Ma, *Member, IEEE*, Li Hao, *Member, IEEE* and George K. Karagiannidis, *Fellow, IEEE*

Abstract—We propose an indoor lightwave downlink wireless communication network with non-orthogonal multiple access (NOMA), consisting of one visible light communication (VLC) access point (AP) and a pair of randomly located users. Although both users can directly receive information from the AP, the performance of the far user is degraded compared to the near one, due to the asymmetrical channel gains. Thus, we propose user cooperation to improve the performance of the far user, by using mixed VLC/RF relaying in parallel with the wireless optical direct link. In order to efficiently exploit the advantage of this hybrid system, the concept of cross-band selection combining (CBSC) is introduced, while its performance is thoroughly investigated and compared to appropriate baselines, according to which the far user is continuously served by either the mixed VLC/RF or the direct VLC link. To this end, we derive closed-form expressions for the outage probability of each user as well as the system sum throughput. Finally, simulation results are provided to verify the effectiveness of the proposed scheme and the accuracy of the corresponding analysis. **Index Terms**—Lightwave, hybrid system, decode-and-forward relaying, non-orthogonal multiple access (NOMA), cross band selection combining (CBSC).

I. INTRODUCTION

THE main challenge to meet the ever-growing demands for high connectivity, reliability and data rates in the fifth generation (5G) of communication networks and beyond, is the saturation of the radio frequency (RF) spectrum. This problem, if not properly addressed, can create a bottleneck in the performance of future wireless networks, the development of novel applications as well as the potential profits of the communications service providers. In order to deal with the aforementioned challenges, the integration of optical spectrum in the design of wireless communication systems has been considered as a promising direction to deal with the spectrum scarcity problem. Consequently, the effective utilization of wireless technologies operating across RF and optical spectrum bands under a *cross-band design* in the PHY and MAC layers is of paramount importance, with the aim to increase not only the available spectrum but also the overall spectral efficiency.

Y. Xiao, Z. Fang, Z. Ma, and L. Hao are with the Provincial Key Lab of Information Coding and Transmission, Southwest Jiaotong University, Chengdu 610031, China (e-mails: alice_xiaoyue@hotmail.com ; fangzequn@my.swjtu.edu.cn; {zma, lhao}@home.swjtu.edu.cn).

P. D. Diamantoulakis, George K. Karagiannidis are with the Provincial Key Lab of Information Coding and Transmission, Southwest Jiaotong University, Chengdu 610031, China, and also with the Electrical and Computer Engineering Department, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Thessaloniki 54124, Greece (e-mail: {padiaman, geokarag}@auth.gr).

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A. Motivation

Visible light communication (VLC) occupies the frequency range from 400 THz to 800 THz, while RF holds the spectrum from 3 KHz to 300 GHz [1], [2]. VLC has recently attracted both academic and industrial interest, due to the inherent advantages of optical communication systems [1]–[6], as well as the adoption of the easy-to-modulate light emitting diodes (LEDs) in common lighting applications, which enables the utilization of existing lighting infrastructure for communication purposes. With the two-fold exploitation of LEDs-based systems, a vast amount of unused electromagnetic spectrum in the visible light region is enabled, which can be used to offer very high data rate and multi-connectivity. Moreover, VLC can provide enhanced security (light can be confined within a room), no electromagnetic interference, easy bandwidth reuse, increased energy efficiency and considerable energy savings, no RF contamination and immunity to RF interference, low cost, etc. Due to these advantages, VLC has been recognized as a promising alternative/complementary technology to RF, that can facilitate access to devices, especially in indoor applications, and is one of the potential candidate technologies in the 5G Public-Private-Partnership (PPP) [7]. The main challenges of VLC include users' mobility, as well as the mitigation of severe channel degradation at the absence of a strong direct link [8]. A promising direction to overcome these challenges is the utilization of hybrid VLC/RF systems [9]–[12], where RF and VLC are employed in a dual-hop configuration in order to extend the coverage and increase the quality-of-service (QoS) of VLC systems.

On the other hand, connectivity and spectral efficiency, which are the major objectives of the proposed cross-band design, can be increased through non-orthogonal multiple access (NOMA) [13]. It is noted that NOMA has already been an approved study item of the 3-rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) in Release 15 [14]. According to NOMA, multiple users' messages can be superposed on the power domain, while the successive interference cancellation (SIC) can be adopted at the receiver side to distinguish the desired signals for each user [15]. One of the major challenges in power-domain NOMA is the fairness-aware resource allocation among users in order to strengthen the transmission reliability for the user who suffers from weaker channel conditions and/or stronger interference [16]–[19]. NOMA protocol has also been recently investigated in the context of VLC communications networks [20]–[22]. More specifically, to enhance spectral efficiency and fairness in the NOMA-VLC

transparent to the communication at the RF band, U_1 operates in full-duplex mode [25], i.e., it simultaneously receives and transmits information. In practice, the received symbol by U_2 at the RF band is delayed by one timeslot, i.e., during timeslot j , U_2 receives the symbols $x_{2,j}$ and $x_{2,j-1}$ by the VLC AP and U_1 , respectively. However, for a sufficiently high number of transmitted symbols, the impact of this delay on the system's performance is insignificant and can be ignored. Moreover, the timing synchronization for hybrid RF/free space optical (FSO) systems is already discussed in [26].

With the assumption that instantaneous channel information is not known at the transmitter nodes, a fixed rate requirement is considered for each receiver, with Γ_1 and Γ_2 being the target rates for U_1 and U_2 , respectively. In this case, the key performance metrics are the outage probability and system throughput.

A. VLC Transmission

The VLC AP transmits x_v , which is the superposition of the optical signals that correspond to U_1 and U_2 , respectively, and can be expressed as

$$x_v = \beta_1 \alpha A x_1 + \beta_2 \alpha A x_2. \quad (1)$$

In (1), x_1 and x_2 are the messages to the users U_1 and U_2 , respectively, with normalized power, i.e., $\mathbb{E}(x_1) = \mathbb{E}(x_2) = 1$, where $\mathbb{E}(\cdot)$ denotes expectation, and β_1 and β_2 are the corresponding power allocation values, which are subject to the constraint $\beta_1 + \beta_2 = 1$. Also, A and $\xi = \alpha A$ denote the peak and average illumination, where α is the corresponding illumination parameter. Due to these constraints, the average illumination should satisfy

$$\beta_1 \alpha A + \beta_2 \alpha A = \xi. \quad (2)$$

Accordingly, the received optical signal at the U_i can be expressed as

$$y_i = h_i x_v + n_i, \quad i \in \{1, 2\}, \quad (3)$$

where n_i is defined as the additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN). Also, h_i denotes the VLC channel gain from the VLC AP to the i -th user, which is given by [27],

$$h_i = \frac{(m+1)A_r}{2\pi d_i^2} \cos^m(\phi_i) T(\psi_i) g(\psi_i) \cos(\psi_i), \quad (4)$$

where A_r is the detector area of the i -th user, ϕ_i and ψ_i are the irradiance and incidence angles of the i -th user, respectively, and the Lambertian emission order m can be obtained by

$$m = -\ln 2 / \ln(\cos \Phi_{1/2}), \quad (5)$$

with $\Phi_{1/2}$ being the transmitter semi-angle corresponding to the half illumination power. Moreover, $d_i = \sqrt{r_i^2 + L^2}$ denotes the distance between the VLC AP and the i -th user. Assuming that the optical detector of each user side is vertical to the horizontal plane, it holds that $\phi_i \approx \psi_i$. Besides, $T(\psi_i)$ and $g(\psi_i)$ are defined as the gains of the optical filter and

optical concentrator, respectively. Moreover, the idealized gain of nonimaging optical concentrator is given in [27], as

$$g(\psi_i) = \begin{cases} \frac{n^2}{\sin^2 \Psi_C} & , 0 \leq \psi_i \leq \Psi_C \\ 0 & , \psi_i > \Psi_C, \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

where Ψ_C denotes the receiver's filed-of-view and n is the internal refractive index, which takes a typical value between 1 to 2 for visible light.

As it becomes evident from (4), h_i is affected directly by the distance between the VLC AP and i -th user. Also, recalling that U_1 and U_2 are assumed to be uniformly distributed or scattered randomly in a disk of radius R_0 and an annular area bounded by $[R_0, R_v]$, respectively, the polar coordinates of each user (r_i, θ_i) follow the uniform distribution. The channel gain in (4) can easily be expressed as a function of the users' location, as in [21], i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned} h_i &= \frac{(m+1)A_r T(\psi_i) g(\psi_i)}{2\pi} \frac{L^{(m+1)}}{(r_i^2 + L^2)^{\frac{m+3}{2}}} \\ &= \frac{C(m+1)L^{(m+1)}}{(r_i^2 + L^2)^{\frac{m+3}{2}}}, \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where $C = \frac{A_r T(\psi_i) g(\psi_i)}{2\pi}$.

To derive the cumulative density function (CDF) of the channel power gains, we define $Y_i = |h_i|^2$, $Y_i \in [Y_{i,\min}, Y_{i,\max}]$, which receives its minimum and maximum value when the user is located at $r_{i,\min}$ and $r_{i,\max}$, respectively. Moreover, by plugging $r_1 \in [0, R_0]$ and $r_2 \in [R_0, R_v]$ into (7), the ranges for Y_1 and Y_2 can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} [Y_{1,\min}, Y_{1,\max}] &= \left[\frac{(C(m+1)L^{(m+1)})^2}{(R_0^2 + L^2)^{(m+3)}}, \frac{(C(m+1)L^{(m+1)})^2}{L^{2(m+3)}} \right], \\ [Y_{2,\min}, Y_{2,\max}] &= \left[\frac{(C(m+1)L^{(m+1)})^2}{(R_v^2 + L^2)^{(m+3)}}, \frac{(C(m+1)L^{(m+1)})^2}{(R_0^2 + L^2)^{(m+3)}} \right], \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

respectively. Subsequently, the corresponding CDF of Y_i can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} F_{|h_i|^2}(y) &= \Pr \left[\frac{(C(m+1)L^{(m+1)})^2}{(r_i^2 + L^2)^{m+3}} < y \right] \\ &= 1 - \Pr [r_i < T(y)], \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where $T(y)$ is defined as

$$T(y) = \sqrt{\left(\frac{(C(m+1)L^{(m+1)})^2}{y} \right)^{\frac{1}{3+m}} - L^2}.$$

Recalling the assumption of uniform distribution for r_1 and r_2 , the corresponding probability density functions (PDFs) can be written as

$$f_{r_1}(d_1) = \frac{2d_1}{R_0^2}, \quad 0 \leq d_1 \leq R_0, \quad (10)$$

and

$$f_{r_2}(d_2) = \frac{2(d_2 - R_0)}{(R_v - R_0)^2}, \quad R_0 \leq d_2 \leq R_v, \quad (11)$$

respectively. Therefore, by integrating $f_{r_i}(d_i)$ over the dedicated $[d_{i,\min}, d_{i,\max}]$, the corresponding CDFs can be expressed as

$$F_{r_1}(d_1) = \frac{d_1^2}{R_0^2}, \quad 0 \leq d_1 \leq R_0, \quad (12)$$

and

$$F_{r_2}(d_2) = \frac{d_2^2 + R_0^2 - 2R_0d_2}{(R_v - R_0)^2}, \quad R_0 \leq d_2 \leq R_v. \quad (13)$$

Consequently, the CDF of Y_i can be obtained by substituting (9) and (12) into (13), as

$$F_{|h_1|^2}(y_1) = \begin{cases} 1 - \frac{T(y_1)^2}{R_0^2} & , Y_{1,\min} \leq y_1 \leq Y_{1,\max} \\ 1 & , y_1 > Y_{1,\max} \\ 0 & , y_1 < Y_{1,\min} \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

and

$$F_{|h_2|^2}(y_2) = \begin{cases} 1 - \frac{T(y_2)^2 - 2R_0T(y_2) + R_0^2}{(R_v - R_0)^2} & , Y_{2,\min} \leq y_2 \leq Y_{2,\max} \\ 1 & , y_2 > Y_{2,\max} \\ 0 & , y_2 < Y_{2,\min}. \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

Moreover, for VLC with intensity modulation-direct detection (IM-DD) [28], [29], the capacity cannot be described by the traditional Shannon formula, commonly used in RF systems, due to the following inherent characteristics:

- non-negativity of input x_v : the input signal modulates the optical intensity of the emitted light, as a result, the input signal x_v is non-negative and proportional to the light intensity, while the photodetector produces an output signal which is proportional to the detected intensity, corrupted by AWGN.
- peak optical power \mathcal{A} and average optical power ξ constraints: In VLC systems, the control of the transmitted optical power is vital for safety reasons, and/or for dimming control in order to satisfy the illumination requirements in VLC systems.

Furthermore, in power domain NOMA, the stronger user, i.e., U_1 , first decodes the message of the weaker user with rate $\mathcal{R}_{2 \rightarrow 1, V}$, and then obtains its own message with rate $\mathcal{R}_{1, V}$. On the other hand, the weaker user, i.e., U_2 , decodes its own message with rate $\mathcal{R}_{2, V}$, by handling x_1 as interference. Due to SIC procedure in power domain NOMA, the desired information x_1 can be obtained at U_1 only after decoding the x_2 successfully. Considering all the above particularities of NOMA VLC systems, the achievable rates $\mathcal{R}_{2 \rightarrow 1, V}$, $\mathcal{R}_{1, V}$, and $\mathcal{R}_{2, V}$ can be described by the corresponding capacity lower bounds that have been derived in [29] and can be written as

$$\mathcal{R}_{2 \rightarrow 1, V} = \left[\log_2 \left(1 + \frac{\beta_2^2 (\alpha \mathcal{A})^2 |h_1|^2}{(\beta_1^2 (\alpha \mathcal{A})^2 |h_1|^2 + 9\sigma^2)(1 + \epsilon_\mu)^2} \right) - \epsilon_\phi \right]^+, \quad (16)$$

$$\mathcal{R}_{1, V} = \left[\log_2 \left(1 + \frac{\beta_1^2 (\alpha \mathcal{A})^2 |h_1|^2}{9\sigma^2(1 + \epsilon_\mu)^2} \right) - \epsilon_\phi \right]^+, \quad (17)$$

and

$$\mathcal{R}_{2, V} = \left[\log_2 \left(1 + \frac{\beta_2^2 (\alpha \mathcal{A})^2 |h_2|^2}{(\beta_1^2 (\alpha \mathcal{A})^2 |h_2|^2 + 9\sigma^2)(1 + \epsilon_\mu)^2} \right) - \epsilon_\phi \right]^+, \quad (18)$$

where $[\cdot]^+ = \max(0, \cdot)$, $\epsilon_\phi = 0.016$, $\epsilon_\mu = 0.0015$, σ^2 is the noise variance [29].

B. RF transmission

The received signal by U_2 at the RF frequency band is

$$y_R = \sqrt{P_r} x_2 h_R + n_R, \quad (19)$$

where $h_R \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, d_R^{-\nu})$ is the RF channel gain between U_1 and U_2 , which is assumed to exhibit independent and identical Rayleigh fading, with d_R being calculated by the Euclidean distance as

$$d_R = \sqrt{r_1^2 + r_2^2 - 2r_1r_2 \cos(\theta_2 - \theta_1)} \quad (20)$$

and ν being the path loss parameter. Also, n_R is the AWGN noise at the RF receiver of U_2 , with average power σ_R^2 . Thus, according to Shannon capacity, the achievable data rate for the information transmission between U_1 and U_2 via the RF link is [13]

$$\mathcal{R}_{2, R} = \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{P_r |h_R|^2}{\sigma_R^2} \right). \quad (21)$$

III. FIXED POLICIES

In this section, two fixed baseline policies are investigated in terms of outage probability and system throughput, according to which either the VLC direct link or the cooperative RF link from U_1 to U_2 is continuously used for information decoding by U_2 . Hereinafter, $P_r[\cdot]$ denotes probability of an event.

A. VLC and RF cooperative link

This subsection focuses on the scenario that the superposition signal transmitted by the VLC AP is exploited solely by U_1 , while U_2 only uses the signal transmitted from U_1 over the RF frequency band for information decoding. As one can easily observe, in this case, U_2 can successfully decode its message only if it is successfully decoded by U_1 . Next, the outage probability for each user is defined and analyzed.

1) *Outage probability for U_1* : Assuming that Γ_i is the required threshold transmission rate of the desired message x_i for U_i , then the outage probability for U_1 is defined as the probability that the achievable rate of the desired x_1 at U_1 is smaller than its corresponding Γ_1 , which also depends on the SIC procedure.

Theorem 1. *The outage probability for U_1 can be expressed in closed-form as*

$$P_{O, \text{VLC}}^1 = \begin{cases} 1 - \frac{T(\zeta^*)^2}{R_0^2} & , \gamma_2 < \frac{\beta_2^2}{\beta_1^2} \\ 1 & , \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (22)$$

where

$$\gamma_i = (2^{\Gamma_i + \epsilon_\phi} - 1)(1 + \epsilon_\mu)^2, \quad (23a)$$

$$\zeta^* = \min\{\max\{\zeta_1, Y_{1,\min}\}, Y_{1,\max}\}, \quad (23b)$$

$$\zeta = \max\{\zeta_1, \zeta_2\}, \quad (23c)$$

$$\zeta_1 = \frac{9\gamma_1}{(\beta_1^2)(\alpha\rho_v)^2}, \quad (23d)$$

$$\zeta_2 = \frac{9\gamma_2}{(\beta_2^2 - \beta_1^2\gamma_2)(\alpha\rho_v)^2}. \quad (23e)$$

Proof. The outage probability for U_1 is defined as

$$\begin{aligned} P_{\text{O,VLC}}^1 &\stackrel{(a)}{=} \text{P}_r[\mathcal{R}_{2 \rightarrow 1, V} < \Gamma_2] + \\ &\quad \text{P}_r[\mathcal{R}_{2 \rightarrow 1, V} > \Gamma_2, \mathcal{R}_{1, V} < \Gamma_1] \\ &\stackrel{(b)}{=} 1 - \text{P}_r[\mathcal{R}_{2 \rightarrow 1, V} > \Gamma_2 \cap \mathcal{R}_{1, V} > \Gamma_1], \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

where step (a) follows from the fact that the desired x_1 can be received only after decoding x_2 successfully, which also can be expressed as the complementary event of successful decoding by using step (b). Next, by plugging (16) and (17) into above (24), $P_{\text{O,VLC}}^1$ can be deduced as

$$P_{\text{O,VLC}}^1 = \begin{cases} F_{|h_1|^2}(\zeta^*) & , \gamma_2 < \frac{\beta_2^2}{\beta_1^2} \\ 1 & , \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (25)$$

Consequently, by substituting (14) into (25), we can obtain a closed-form expression as given in (22) and then the proof is completed. \square

2) *Outage probability for U_2 :* When the mixed VLC/RF relaying link is used, the outage probability for U_2 can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} P_{\text{O,VLC/RF}}^2 &= \text{P}_r[\min\{\mathcal{R}_{2 \rightarrow 1, V}, \mathcal{R}_{2, R}\} < \Gamma_2] \\ &= 1 - \text{P}_r[\mathcal{R}_{2 \rightarrow 1, V} > \Gamma_2 \cap \mathcal{R}_{2, R} > \Gamma_2] \\ &\stackrel{(c)}{=} 1 - \text{P}_r[\mathcal{R}_{2 \rightarrow 1, V} > \Gamma_2] \text{P}_r[\mathcal{R}_{2, R} > \Gamma_2 | \mathcal{R}_{2 \rightarrow 1, V} > \Gamma_2], \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

where step (c) follows the fact that channels h_1 and h_R are not independent due to the impact of the users' locations on RF link, according to (20). Then, by using similar steps as in the proof of Theorem 1, the following expression is derived:

$$\text{P}_r[\mathcal{R}_{2 \rightarrow 1, V} > \Gamma_2] = \begin{cases} \text{P}_r[r_1 < r_1^c] & , \gamma_2 < \frac{\beta_2^2}{\beta_1^2} \\ 1 & , \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (27)$$

where

$$r_1^c = \sqrt{\left(\frac{(C(m+1)L^{(m+1)})^2}{\zeta_{2,1}^*}\right)^{\frac{1}{3+m}} - L^2}, \quad (28)$$

and

$$\zeta_{2,1}^* = \min\{\max\{\zeta_2, Y_{1, \min}\}, Y_{1, \max}\}. \quad (29)$$

Next, under the assumption of Rayleigh fading over the RF link and by using (27), the conditional probability of $[\mathcal{R}_{2, R} > \Gamma_2]$ given $[\mathcal{R}_{2 \rightarrow 1, V} > \Gamma_2]$ in (26), can be calculated as

$$\begin{aligned} &\text{P}_r[\mathcal{R}_{2, R} > \Gamma_2 | \mathcal{R}_{2 \rightarrow 1, V} > \Gamma_2] \\ &= \text{P}_r[\mathcal{R}_{2, R} > \Gamma_2 | r_1 < r_1^c] = \text{P}_r[|h_R|^2 > \frac{\gamma_R}{\rho_r} | r_1 < r_1^c] \\ &= e^{-\frac{\gamma_R}{d_R^v \rho_r}}, \quad r_1 < r_1^c, \end{aligned} \quad (30)$$

where $\gamma_R = 2^{\Gamma_2} - 1$, and the distance d_R given in (20) with v being assumed as an even number, for mathematical tractability. [30]

Moreover, by taking into account the randomness of users location, θ_i is also uniformly distributed in the interval $[0, 2\pi]$ and its PDF is given by $f_{\theta_i}(x) = \frac{1}{2\pi}$ ($i \in \{1, 2\}$), thus we

rewrite (26) while considering the limited area given in (28), as

$$P_{\text{O,VLC/RF}}^2 = 1 - \mathbb{E}\left[e^{-\frac{\gamma_R}{d_R^v \rho_r}}\right], \quad r_1 < r_1^c. \quad (31)$$

Theorem 2. *A closed-form expression in the high SNR regime for the outage probability for U_2 is*

$$P_{\text{O,VLC/RF}}^2 = \frac{\gamma_R}{\pi^2 R_0^2 (R_v - R_0)^2 \rho_r} \sum_{k=0}^{v/2} \binom{v/2}{k} (-1)^{\frac{v}{2}-k} J_1 J_2 \quad (32)$$

with

$$\begin{aligned} J_1 &= \sum_{q=0}^{v/2-k} \binom{v/2-k}{q} \left[B\left(\frac{v/2-k-q+1}{2}, \frac{q+1}{2}\right) \right. \\ &\quad \left. \times \frac{(1 + (-1)^{\frac{v}{2}-k-q})(1 + (-1)^q)}{2} \right]^2 (-1)^{\frac{v}{2}-k-q}, \end{aligned} \quad (33)$$

where $B(x, y)$ is the beta function [31]. Moreover, a closed-form expression of J_2 is given by

$$\begin{aligned} J_2 &= 2^{\frac{v}{2}-k} \sum_{l=0}^k \binom{k}{l} \frac{1}{2l + \frac{v}{2} - k + 2} (r_1^c)^{2l + \frac{v}{2} - k + 2} \times \\ &\quad \left[\frac{1}{k - 2l + \frac{v}{2} + 2} (R_v^{k-2l + \frac{v}{2} + 2} - R_0^{k-2l + \frac{v}{2} + 2}) \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \frac{R_0}{k - 2l + \frac{v}{2} + 1} (R_v^{k-2l + \frac{v}{2} + 1} - R_0^{k-2l + \frac{v}{2} + 1}) \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (34)$$

Proof. To obtain a closed-form expression, we consider the expectation operation $\mathbb{E}\left[e^{-\frac{\gamma_R}{d_R^v \rho_r}}\right]$ in the high SNR regime, by using the approximation $e^{(-x)}|_{x \rightarrow 0} \approx 1 - x$. Thus,

$$e^{-\frac{\gamma_R}{d_R^v \rho_r}} \approx 1 - \frac{\gamma_R}{\rho_r (r_1^2 + r_2^2 - 2r_1 r_2 \cos(\theta_2 - \theta_1))^{(v/2)}}. \quad (35)$$

As users are randomly deployed, it holds that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}\left[e^{-\frac{\gamma_R}{d_R^v \rho_r}}\right] &\approx 1 - \frac{\gamma_R}{\pi^2 R_0^2 (R_v - R_0)^2 \rho_r} \underbrace{\int_{R_0}^{R_v} \int_0^{r_1^c} \int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} (r_2 - R_0) \\ &\quad \underbrace{r_1 (r_1^2 + r_2^2 - 2r_1 r_2 \cos(\theta_2 - \theta_1))^{(v/2)} d\theta_1 d\theta_2 dr_1 dr_2}_{J}. \end{aligned} \quad (36)$$

While considering the independence of the variables (radius and angle) in the users' polar coordinates (r_i, θ_i) , (36) can be further reduced into two separate double integrals, i.e., radial-based and angle-based integrals. Moreover, by applying binomial theorem, J in (36) can be rewritten as

$$\begin{aligned} J &= \sum_{k=0}^{v/2} \binom{v/2}{k} (-1)^{\frac{v}{2}-k} \underbrace{\int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} \cos^{\frac{v}{2}-k}(\theta_2 - \theta_1) d\theta_1 d\theta_2}_{J_1} \\ &\quad \underbrace{\int_{R_0}^{R_v} \int_0^{r_1^c} (r_1^2 + r_2^2)^k (2r_1 r_2)^{\frac{v}{2}-k} r_1 (r_2 - R_0) dr_1 dr_2}_{J_2}, \end{aligned} \quad (37)$$

Considering Lemma 2 in [30], (33) can be derived by utilizing the equation (2.5.12.44) in [31] and the sum-difference formulas of trigonometric functions. Moreover, by considering the constrained areas of U_1 and U_2 , we can evaluate the double-integral J_2 as

$$\begin{aligned} J_2 &= \int_{R_0}^{R_v} \int_0^{r_1^c} (r_1^2 + r_2^2)^k (2r_1 r_2)^{\frac{v}{2}-k} r_1 (r_2 - R_0) dr_1 dr_2, \\ &= 2^{\frac{v}{2}-k} \sum_{l=0}^k \binom{k}{l} \int_0^{r_1^c} r_1^{(2l+\frac{v}{2}-k+1)} dr_1 \times \\ &\quad \left[\int_{R_0}^{R_v} r_2^{(k-2l+\frac{v}{2}-1)} dr_2 - R_0 \int_{R_0}^{R_v} r_2^{(k-2l+\frac{v}{2})} dr_2 \right], \end{aligned} \quad (38)$$

from which (34) is derived.

By substituting (36), (37), (33) and (34) into (31), (32) is derived and the proof is completed. \square

B. Direct VLC link

In this subsection, we investigate the policy according to which U_2 directly receives its message from the VLC AP, i.e., mixed VLC/RF relaying is never used.

Theorem 3. *When only the wireless optical link is used, the outage probability for U_2 can be expressed as*

$$P_{O,VLC}^2 = \begin{cases} 1 - \frac{T(\zeta_{2,2}^*)^2 - 2R_0 T(\zeta_{2,2}^*) + R_0^2}{(R_v - R_0)^2}, & \gamma_2 < \frac{\beta_2^2}{\beta_1^2} \\ 1, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (39)$$

where

$$\zeta_{2,2}^* = \min\{\max\{\zeta_2, Y_{2,min}\}, Y_{2,max}\}. \quad (40)$$

Proof. According to the decoding procedure, in this case holds that

$$\begin{aligned} P_{O,VLC}^2 &= P_r[\mathcal{R}_{2,V} < \Gamma_2] \\ &= \begin{cases} F_{|h_2|^2}(\zeta_{2,2}^*) & , \gamma_2 < \frac{\beta_2^2}{\beta_1^2} \\ 1 & , \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (41)$$

Then, a closed-form expression for the outage probability for U_2 can be obtained by using (15) and (41) and the proof is completed. \square

C. System Sum Throughput

In order to characterize the successful message delivery over the communication channels, sum throughput is provided as follows while taking into account the predefined target rates Γ_i . The system sum throughput for the two fixed policies can be expressed by utilizing their corresponding outage probabilities, as

$$R_{VLC/RF} = (1 - P_{O,VLC}^1) \Gamma_1 + (1 - P_{O,VLC/RF}^2) \Gamma_2 \quad (42)$$

and

$$R_{VLC} = (1 - P_{O,VLC}^1) \Gamma_1 + (1 - P_{O,VLC}^2) \Gamma_2, \quad (43)$$

respectively, where the specific closed-form expressions of the outage probabilities (i.e., $P_{O,VLC}^1$, $P_{O,VLC/RF}^2$, $P_{O,VLC}^2$) have been provided in (22), (32) and (39).

IV. CROSS-BAND SELECTION COMBINING

A cross-band selection combining policy (CBSC) is introduced according to which U_2 uses the best from the two links, i.e., the mixed VLC/RF and the direct one, to decode its message. Consequently, CBSC is expected to reduce the outage probability for U_2 compared to the fixed policies presented in the previous section. CBSC is also motivated by the fact that although U_2 receives two copies of its message over the two bands, linear coherent combining technique (e.g. MRC) is not applicable to this scenario.

A. Outage Probability Analysis

When CBSC is used, the outage probability at U_2 is defined as the probability that the outage probability for the proposed CBSC is defined as that the achievable rate at combiner output (both RF receiver and lightwave receiver) is smaller than a predefined target rate [32]. Accordingly, the outage probability in this scheme can be determined by

$$\begin{aligned} P_{O,CBSC}^2 &= P_r[\mathcal{O}_2^{VLC} \cap \mathcal{O}_2^{VLC+RF}] \\ &= P_r[\mathcal{O}_2^{VLC}] P_r[\mathcal{O}_2^{VLC/RF} | \mathcal{O}_2^{VLC}]. \end{aligned} \quad (44)$$

For simplicity and tractability, $\mathcal{O}_2^{VLC/RF}$ and \mathcal{O}_2^{VLC} are denoted as the outage events of the message x_2 performing at the far user U_2 , from the direct VLC link and the mixed VLC/RF relaying link, respectively. In order to analyze the conditional probability in (44), we first define the probability of event $[\mathcal{O}_2^{VLC}]$ as

$$P_r[\mathcal{O}_2^{VLC}] = P_r[\mathcal{R}_{2,V} < \Gamma_2] = P_r[r_2 > r_2^c], \quad (45)$$

where the constrained distance r_2^c of the far user is

$$r_2^c = \sqrt{\left(\frac{(C(m+1)L^{(m+1)})^2}{\zeta_{2,2}^*} \right)^{\frac{1}{3+m}} - L^2}. \quad (46)$$

Subsequently, the outage event $\mathcal{O}_2^{VLC/RF}$ can be decomposed into two cases: i) decoding x_2 at U_1 using VLC link is not successful; ii) x_2 can be decoded by U_1 correctly but maintains in outage condition via the RF link from U_1 to U_2 . Thus, the corresponding outage probability can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} P_r[\mathcal{O}_2^{VLC/RF}] &= P_r[\mathcal{R}_{2 \rightarrow 1, V} < \Gamma_2] \\ &\quad + P_r[\mathcal{R}_{2, R} < \Gamma_2 | \mathcal{R}_{2 \rightarrow 1, V} > \Gamma_2] \\ &= P_r[r_1 > r_1^c] + P_r[|h_R|^2 < \frac{\gamma_R}{\rho_r} | r_1 < r_1^c]. \end{aligned} \quad (47)$$

Comprehensively consider the above two outage events, we have

$$\begin{aligned} P_r[\mathcal{O}_2^{VLC/RF} | \mathcal{O}_2^{VLC}] &= P_r[r_1 > r_1^c, r_2 > r_2^c] \\ &\quad + P_r[|h_R|^2 < \frac{\gamma_R}{\rho_r} | (r_1 < r_1^c, r_2 > r_2^c)]. \end{aligned} \quad (48)$$

Theorem 4. While considering the randomness of users' locations, the outage probability for U_2 can be expressed in closed-form, as

$$\begin{aligned} P_{O, \text{CBSC}}^2 &= \frac{2(R_0^2 - (r_1^c)^2)}{R_0^2(R_v - R_0)^2} \left(\frac{1}{2}R_v^2 - R_0R_v - \frac{1}{2}(r_2^c)^2 + R_0r_2^c \right) \\ &+ \frac{\gamma_R}{\pi^2 R_0^2 (R_v - R_0)^2 \rho_r} \sum_{k=0}^{v/2} \binom{v/2}{k} (-1)^{\frac{v}{2}-k} J_1 J_{2, \text{CBSC}}, \end{aligned} \quad (49)$$

where J_1 is given in (33) and $J_{2, \text{CBSC}}$ can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} J_{2, \text{CBSC}} &= 2^{\frac{v}{2}-k} \sum_{l=0}^k \binom{k}{l} \frac{1}{2l + \frac{v}{2} - k + 2} (r_1^c)^{2l + \frac{v}{2} - k + 2} \\ &\times \left[\frac{1}{k - 2l + \frac{v}{2} + 2} (R_v^{k-2l + \frac{v}{2} + 2} - (r_2^c)^{k-2l + \frac{v}{2} + 2}) \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \frac{R_0}{k - 2l + \frac{v}{2} + 1} (R_v^{k-2l + \frac{v}{2} + 1} - (r_2^c)^{k-2l + \frac{v}{2} + 1}) \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (50)$$

Proof. Considering the randomly deployed users in the constrained area, the average of the first term in (48) can be obtained as

$$\begin{aligned} P_r[r_1 > r_1^c, r_2 > r_2^c] &= \int_{r_2^c}^{R_v} \int_{r_1^c}^{R_0} \frac{2r_1}{R_0^2} \frac{2(r_2 - R_0)}{(R_v - R_0)^2} d_{r_1} d_{r_2} \\ &= \frac{2(R_0^2 - (r_1^c)^2)}{R_0^2(R_v - R_0)^2} \left(\frac{1}{2}R_v^2 - R_0R_v - \frac{1}{2}(r_2^c)^2 + R_0r_2^c \right). \end{aligned} \quad (51)$$

As for the second term in (48), the Euclidean distance between U_1 and U_2 through RF link in our system should also be taken into account, i.e., $d_R = \sqrt{r_1^2 + r_2^2 - 2r_1r_2 \cos(\theta_2 - \theta_1)}$, thus, we calculate the average outage probability by utilizing the users' polar coordinates, according to which

$$\begin{aligned} P_r[|h_R|^2 < \frac{\gamma_R}{\rho_r} | (r_1 < r_1^c, r_2 > r_2^c)] &\stackrel{(d)}{\approx} \frac{\gamma_R}{\rho_r (r_1^2 + r_2^2 - 2r_1r_2 \cos(\theta_2 - \theta_1))^{(v/2)}} \\ &= \frac{\gamma_R}{\pi^2 R_0^2 (R_v - R_0)^2 \rho_r} \int_{r_2^c}^{R_v} \int_0^{r_1^c} \int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} r_1 (r_2 - R_0) \\ &\quad (r_1^2 + r_2^2 - 2r_1r_2 \cos(\theta_2 - \theta_1))^{(v/2)} d_{\theta_1} d_{\theta_2} d_{r_1} d_{r_2}, \end{aligned} \quad (52)$$

where step (d) follows from the high SNR approximation, i.e.,

$1 - e^{(-x)}|_{x \rightarrow 0} \approx x$. Then (52) can be further expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} P_r[|h_R|^2 < \frac{\gamma_R}{\rho_r} | (r_1 < r_1^c, r_2 > r_2^c)] &\approx \frac{\gamma_R}{\pi^2 R_0^2 (R_v - R_0)^2 \rho_r} \sum_{k=0}^{v/2} \binom{v/2}{k} (-1)^{\frac{v}{2}-k} \\ &\times \underbrace{\int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} \cos^{(\frac{v}{2}-k)}(\theta_2 - \theta_1) d_{\theta_1} d_{\theta_2}}_{J_1} \\ &\times \underbrace{\int_{r_2^c}^{R_v} \int_0^{r_1^c} (r_1^2 + r_2^2)^k (2r_1r_2)^{\frac{v}{2}-k} r_1 (r_2 - R_0) d_{r_1} d_{r_2}}_{J_{2, \text{CBSC}}}, \end{aligned} \quad (53)$$

where a closed-form expression of J_1 is given in (33). Then, by recalling the procedure in (38) but with different constraints of the users' locations, i.e., $[0, r_1^c]$, $[r_2^c, R_v]$, $J_{2, \text{CBSC}}$ can be deduced as (50).

Finally, we can obtain the analytical expression for $P_{O, \text{CBSC}}^2$ by plugging (51), (52) into (48) and the proof is completed. \square

B. Bounds on the Outage Probability

In order to intuitively figure out the behavior of the proposed CBSC method while reducing the computational complexity which is high due to the dependency of the direct and mixed VLC/RF links, following the upper and lower bounds are provided [33]. Specifically, the upper and lower bounds of $P_r[\mathcal{O}_2^{\text{VLC}} \cap \mathcal{O}_2^{\text{VLC/RF}}]$ can be achieved by plugging (32) and (39) into the following expressions,

$$P_{O, \text{CBSC}}^{2, \text{upp}} = \min(P_r(\mathcal{O}_2^{\text{VLC}}), P_r(\mathcal{O}_2^{\text{VLC/RF}})) \quad (54)$$

and

$$P_{O, \text{CBSC}}^{2, \text{low}} = P_r(\mathcal{O}_2^{\text{VLC}}) + P_r(\mathcal{O}_2^{\text{VLC/RF}}) - 1, \quad (55)$$

respectively.

C. System Sum Throughput

Along with the outage probability analysis, the system sum throughput of this policy can be written as

$$R_{\text{CBSC}} = (1 - P_{O, \text{VLC}}^1) \Gamma_1 + (1 - P_{O, \text{CBSC}}^2) \Gamma_2, \quad (56)$$

where $P_{O, \text{VLC}}^1$ and $P_{O, \text{CBSC}}^2$ have already expressed in (22) and (49).

V. SIMULATIONS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, Monte Carlo simulations are performed to validate the proposed analytical framework and assess the impact of the VLC AP parameters (i.e., average transmit SNR, semi-angle, vertical height) and the users' power allocation (β_1, β_2) on the system's performance. The values of all parameters are given in Table-I, if not otherwise specified. The performance metrics of the three policies (i.e., the two fixed

TABLE I
SIMULATION PARAMETERS

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
R_0	1.5 m	v	2
R_v	3 m	A_r	1 cm ²
L	2.15 m	Ψ_C	60°
n	1.5	$\Phi_{1/2}$	60°
$T(\psi_i)$	1		

Fig. 2. Outage probability for different average transmit SNR from the VLC AP $(\alpha\rho_v)^2$.

that consider the direct VLC link only or the cooperative VLC-RF link to U_2 and the proposed CBSC) are investigated and compared. Hereinafter, to facilitate reading, ‘‘VLC’’, ‘‘Mixed VLC/RF relaying’’, and ‘‘Proposed CBSC’’ are used to refer to the aforementioned policies.

Fig. 2 illustrates the outage probability of the three different policies versus the average SNR of the VLC AP, i.e., $(\alpha\rho_v)^2$, where the power allocation is set as $\beta_1 = 0.3, \beta_2 = 0.7$, $\Gamma_1 = 1$ bits/transmission, $\Gamma_2 = 1$ bits/transmission. The comparison is performed for the two different SNR settings: $\rho_r = \frac{1}{3}(\alpha\rho_v)^2$ and fixed value of $\rho_r = 30$ dB. Note that the RF transmission is employed in order to help the far user and therefore it makes sense to set the average SNR ρ_r lower than $(\alpha\rho_v)^2$, while considering the system fairness. Then, variable and constant retransmitted RF power ρ_r are both considered to further investigate the impact of the RF link between U_1 and U_2 . Overall, the average outage probability of each user in the different policies decreases, when the SNR increases from 70 dB to 85 dB, except for the U_2 in cooperative VLC-RF link with $\rho_r = 30$ dB. This presents an error floor in the high SNR region, due to the constraint of fixed transmit power over the RF link. Compared with the above cases which consider only the direct VLC link, when the mixed VLC/RF relaying or the proposed CBSC policy are used, we focus on the outage probability for U_2 . Additionally, as it is observed, both the mixed VLC/RF relaying and the proposed CBSC policy can be divided into two regions with different slopes.

Fig. 3. Outage probability for different VLC AP semi-angle $\Phi_{1/2}$.

More specifically, since the direct VLC link to U_2 performs worse compared to the mixed VLC/RF relaying policy, the proposed CBSC is mainly affected by the mixed VLC/RF link. For this reason, the first region of the two policies are almost the same. On the other hand, with an increase of the average transmitted SNR from the VLC AP $(\alpha\rho_v)^2$, CBSC outperforms the mixed VLC/RF relaying policy. Additionally, the upper bound coincides with the cooperative VLC-RF link in this setup, which is in accordance with (54), while the lower bound is tight in the low SNR region.

The outage probabilities for each user in the above three policies are evaluated for several VLC AP semi-angles in Fig. 3, where the results can help to choose the proper value for the parameter. Furthermore, with $\beta_1 = 0.2, \beta_2 = 0.8, \Gamma_1 = 1$ bits/transmission, $\Gamma_2 = 1$ bits/transmission and $(\alpha\rho_v)^2 = 82$ dB, $\rho_r = 30$ dB, the outage probability is illustrated versus the VLC AP semi-angle, which varies from 5° to 60°. For this configuration, it is notable that the outage probability for U_1 in the VLC link can acquire the optimal outage probability for the semi-angle value around 30°.

Next, the outage probabilities are calculated for different realizations of the vertical distance of the VLC AP, which helps to figure out the optimum position of the VLC AP, with $\beta_1 = 0.3, \beta_2 = 0.7, \Gamma_1 = 2$ bits/transmission, $\Gamma_2 = 2$ bits/transmission and $(\alpha\rho_v)^2 = 90$ dB, $\rho_r = 30$ dB. As for the parameters’ values set above, an interesting observation is that setting $L = 3$ m minimizes the outage probability for U_2 when CBSC or the fixed direct VLC policy are utilized. However, the vertical distance of the VLC AP has no significant effect on the outage probabilities for U_2 when the mixed VLC/RF relaying is applied, due to the constant transmitted RF power. However, on the other hand, with the increase of the vertical distance of the VLC AP in the above settings, the outage probability for U_1 also increases.

Furthermore, because of the power-domain NOMA protocol applied in this system, it’s important to investigate the impact of the users’ power allocation on the corresponding outage

Fig. 4. Outage probability for different vertical height of the VLC AP.

Fig. 5. Outage probability for different power allocation β_1 .

probabilities. In Fig. 5, we consider three different cases for the average transmit power, i.e., $(\alpha\rho_v)^2 = \{75, 80, 85\}$ dB and $\rho_r = 30$ dB. As expected, the proposed CBSC performs better than the mixed VLC/RF relaying, in terms of the outage probability for U_2 . However, as the transmitted VLC power increases and more power is allocated to β_1 , the mixed VLC/RF relaying and CBSC asymptotically approach the same outage probability. This finding can be used to achieve a better performance by using proper power allocation. For example, when $(\alpha\rho_v)^2 = 75$ dB, the smallest power allocation leads to the same outage probability for U_2 in the mixed VLC/RF and the proposed CBSC is $\beta_1 = 0.25$, while $\beta_1 = \{0.4, 0.45\}$ corresponding to $(\alpha\rho_v)^2 = \{80, 85\}$ dB, respectively.

On the other hand, in Fig. 6, the system sum throughput is evaluated versus the average VLC AP transmit power $(\alpha\rho_v)^2$ in the range $[88 - 100]$ dB with fixed value $\rho_r = 30$ dB or variables $\rho_r = \frac{1}{3}(\alpha\rho_v)^2$, $\Gamma_1 = 2$ bits/transmission, $\Gamma_2 = 2$

Fig. 6. System sum throughput for different average transmit SNR from the VLC AP.

bits/transmission and $\beta_1 = 0.3, \beta_2 = 0.7$. It is shown that the proposed CBSC is superior to the mixed VLC/RF relaying policy. Note that this results ignore the performance of the direct VLC policy, which is not competitive compared with the other two policies, i.e., the proposed CBSC and the mixed VLC/RF relaying. Furthermore, as the average SNR, i.e., $(\alpha\rho_v)^2$, increases in the high SNR region, the proposed CBSC can also be clarified by noticing the rapid convergence to the total target rate, i.e., 4 bits/transmission.

Fig. 7. Contour plot of system sum throughput versus power allocation β_1 and the average transmit SNR from the VLC AP.

In Fig. 7, the system throughput of the proposed CBSC is illustrated to further investigate the joint effect of the parameters, $(\alpha\rho_v)^2$ and β_1 . We assume that the RF transmitted SNR is $\rho_r = \frac{1}{3}(\alpha\rho_v)^2$ and target rates are $\Gamma_1 = 1$ bits/transmission, $\Gamma_2 = 1$ bits/transmission. By using the results in this figure, we can find the optimal parameter pair $(\beta_1^*, (\alpha\rho_v)^2)$, with the other VLC AP parameters fixed. Consequently, this figure can be used as guide to achieve system performance.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we have introduced a novel cross-band selection combining method for hybrid lightwave/RF cooperative networks with non-orthogonal multiple access. The far user adaptively chooses either the mixed VLC/RF relaying link or the direct VLC link to decode the information, while considering the randomness locations of the near and far user in different annular areas separately. In order to improve the communication quality-of-service for both users, as well to extend the coverage of the network, the CBSC policy is proposed and compared with other two fixed policies, i.e., mixed VLC/RF relaying policy and direct VLC policy. In order to identify the performance of all the policies, closed-form expressions for the outage probability and the system sum throughput in the high SNR region are derived. Moreover, upper and lower bounds for the outage probability of the proposed CBSC are presented to obtain more insights. Finally, simulation results are performed to verify the effectiveness of the proposed CBSC and the accuracy of theoretical study. Specifically, the proposed CBSC offers significant improvement of the weaker user's outage probability and increases the system sum throughput compared to the fixed policies.

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